

Enabling Scalable Vertiport Network Design via Terrain-Aware Spatial Filtering and sPCA-Based Candidate Reduction

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Abstract—Large-scale vertiport network design for Innovative Air Mobility (IAM) faces computational scalability challenges, as regional candidate generation can yield tens of thousands of feasible parcels and millions of binary variables in Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) models. Yet existing methods lack systematic pre-optimization filtering to reduce the decision space while preserving operational and geographic realism. This study proposes a terrain-aware, data-driven spatial reduction strategy that serves as a pre-optimization candidate screening stage and investigates associated computational challenges in regional-scale vertiport network design. By integrating terrain-based distance accumulation with Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA), correlated accessibility and land-use criteria are synthesized into structurally consistent decision-space representations. sPCA mitigates multicollinearity among spatial determinants and extracts dominant structural drivers without subjective weighting. Applied to a regional case study in Saxony, Germany, the framework reduces 74,944 feasible grid cells to 236 candidate locations, decreasing MILP binary variables by two orders of magnitude and reducing solution times from more than 96 hours to 18 minutes under identical solver configurations. The proposed approach enables integration of GIS-based spatial analytics and operations research, supporting geographically consistent and computationally tractable vertiport network planning for large-scale IAM systems.

Keywords—Innovative Air Mobility (IAM), vertiport planning, spatial suitability analysis, Distance Accumulation, Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA)

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban and regional air transportation has emerged under the paradigm of IAM, which integrates low-altitude air vehicles (airspace classes G, E, and D) [1] into existing mobility systems. Within this context, Vertical Takeoff and Landing Aircraft Vertical Takeoff and Landing Aircraft (VCA) are considered a complementary transport mode for passenger and cargo operations over short distances compared to Conventional Commercial Air Transport Conventional Commercial Air Transport (CAT), making them candidates for urban and regional operations. Deployment depends on

vehicle and airspace advances, as well as appropriately designed ground infrastructure. Vertiports constitute—as classic airports do—the critical interface between air and ground networks, and their number, location, and capacity influence system accessibility, cost efficiency, and operational performance requirements for VCA.

Vertiport site selection represents a multi-criteria spatial decision problem characterized by conflicting determinants: accessibility to transport networks, multi-modal integration, land-use compatibility, environmental constraints, safety requirements, and topographic limitations [2]. However, existing methodologies exhibit limitations that reduce applicability. First, many frameworks rely on expert-defined weighting schemes (e.g., AHP, Delphi) that introduce subjectivity and reduce reproducibility [3], [4]. Second, suitability criteria are often assumed statistically independent, neglecting spatial autocorrelation among variables. Third, accessibility is commonly approximated using Euclidean proximity, overlooking terrain constraints and yielding geographically unrealistic patterns [5], [6]. From a network design perspective, optimization models operating on unfiltered candidate sets suffer from combinatorial explosion, leading to high computational costs and spatially impractical solutions [7], [8].

This study proposes a terrain-aware, multi-criteria spatial suitability framework that serves as a pre-optimization ensemble generation stage. The workflow integrates heterogeneous geospatial datasets using terrain-based distance accumulation to represent terrain constraints. Normalized criteria layers are synthesized using Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA), which mitigates multicollinearity and accounts for spatial autocorrelation to extract geographically coherent suitability patterns. High-suitability areas are then transformed into a compact set of optimization-ready candidate locations.

The proposed model is designed to be reproducible, statistically grounded, and transferable across different urban contexts. By automating parameterization and minimizing subjective expert-based weighting, the workflow enhances robustness and reduces analyst-dependent bias. Although demonstrated for vertiport planning, the methodology may be applied generally to infrastructure location problems charac-

terized by multiple spatial constraints and correlated criteria.

Accordingly, this study addresses the following research questions: How can terrain-aware, multi-criteria spatial determinants be systematically integrated and objectively synthesized into a unified suitability model that reveals dominant and geographically coherent spatial structures for vertiport siting? To what extent can suitability-driven candidate generation reduce the computational complexity of subsequent optimization-based network design while preserving spatial realism and operational feasibility?

This study makes the following main contributions. First, it proposes a terrain-aware Geographic Information System (GIS)-based suitability framework that integrates heterogeneous spatial criteria using terrain-based distance accumulation. This allows accessibility to be represented as a surface-constrained process rather than purely Euclidean proximity. Second, it applies Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA) as a data-driven synthesis approach to reduce multicollinearity among criteria and account for spatial autocorrelation, extracting statistically robust spatial suitability structures. Third, it presents a suitability-based candidate filtering procedure that converts continuous suitability surfaces into a reduced set of candidate locations for subsequent network optimization. Collectively, these contributions provide a structured pre-processing approach for reducing the spatial decision space in large-scale Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP)-based IAM infrastructure design.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategic planning and placement of vertiport sites has emerged as a central design task within IAM, with most studies emphasizing the integration of vertiport facilities into existing transportation ecosystems to ensure operational efficiency, intermodal connectivity, and high user acceptance, as is well-known from the existing public transport system. Located close to established mobility hubs, such as airports, major rail stations or metro transfer centres, these installations reduce transfer delays and total door-to-door travel time, thereby improving overall network performance and thus user acceptance [4], [9], [10]. At the local scale, accessibility considerations also influence location decisions. Vertiport locations situated near public transport transits and within walkable service areas are benefiting from facilitated first-last mile connectivity and encouraged adoption [11], [12].

Beyond physical accessibility, demand-oriented approaches prioritize areas characterized by high trip-generation potential and greater willingness to pay. These areas include central business districts, high-activity corridors, and major points of interest, in order to improve utilization rates and economic feasibility [4], [9], [13]. Hence, the estimation of the metrics is merely robust, relying on multiple hypotheses regarding the ramp-up process for IAM [14]. Consequently, vertiport network design should be tolerant to poor forecast quality, not deteriorating the related infrastructure investment. Environmental and social compatibility is also critical, requiring separation from noise-sensitive land uses such as hospitals, schools, and residential zones to ensure regulatory compliance and public acceptance through minimizing ground risk related

IAM routes linking the network nodes [15]. Together, these criteria frame vertiport siting as a multi-criteria spatial decision problem involving heterogeneous and often conflicting determinants.

Methodologically, existing studies typically adopt a staged workflow. Most studies first reduce the decision space through clustering, screening, or multi-criteria suitability assessment, and then refine the reduced candidate set using optimization or simulation. For instance, k -means and density-based clustering approaches are frequently used to generate candidate hubs prior to large-scale integer programming [9], [12], [16]–[18]. Alternatively, expert-driven Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) frameworks combine Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Delphi, and weighted linear combinations within GIS environments to produce suitability maps [3], [4]. While effective, these approaches commonly rely on subjective or expert-defined weighting schemes and often treat suitability criteria as statistically independent. Such assumptions may not explicitly account for potential correlation and spatial dependence among criteria, and spatial dependence among geographic variables, potentially leading to double-counting effects and unstable suitability outcomes. Final placement decisions are often formulated as discrete facility location problems, including hub-location and p -median variants, and solved using MILP or heuristic algorithms [10], [19]–[22].

Recent research further highlights the importance of incorporating terrain and elevation information into IAM planning. High-resolution LIDAR and digital elevation data have been used to construct three-dimensional urban representations that support obstacle avoidance, safe vehicle operations, and terrain-aware distance modeling [5], [7]. From a planning perspective, surface and cost-based spatial analyses increasingly replace simple Euclidean proximity measures, allowing slope, elevation change, and topographic barriers to be explicitly represented as terrain factors in distance calculations [23], [24]. These terrain-aware approaches indicate that accessibility can be represented as a surface-constrained spatial process rather than a purely geometric one.

Despite these advances, existing candidate-reduction approaches in IAM planning predominantly rely on clustering techniques (e.g., k -means or density-based methods) or expert-defined weighting within MCDA frameworks. These strategies primarily emphasize spatial grouping or weighted aggregation of multiple suitability criteria, while statistical correlation, redundancy, and spatial autocorrelation among these criteria are typically not explicitly modeled.

Proximity-, land-use-, and environmental determinants are often strongly correlated, which can bias composite scores and reduce model robustness [25]. While most existing vertiport siting studies rely on expert-driven aggregation or heuristic clustering approaches, statistically grounded, data-driven dimensionality reduction methods such as Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and sPCA have not yet been systematically integrated into vertiport and IAM infrastructure planning frameworks.

To address this methodological gap, the present study proposes a terrain-aware suitability modeling framework that combines terrain-based distance accumulation with sPCA-

Figure 1. Terrain-Aware Spatial Suitability Modeling Framework for Vertipoint Candidate Generation.

based synthesis. This integration enables the systematic treatment of correlated spatial criteria within a pre-optimization candidate generation stage, while explicitly incorporating terrain effects into accessibility modeling.

III. METHODOLOGY

Spatial suitability is defined as a continuous, normalized index (0–1) quantifying the relative appropriateness of each spatial unit for vertipoint deployment, derived from aggregated accessibility, land-use, and environmental criteria. Unlike mathematical optimality, which identifies a single best solution within an optimization model, suitability serves as a pre-optimization screening metric that evaluates locations based on spatial characteristics. Building on this concept, this study develops a terrain-aware spatial suitability modeling framework that synthesizes correlated criteria and incorporates terrain effects into accessibility modeling to systematically reduce the spatial decision space prior to network optimization. As illustrated in Figure 1, the workflow comprises 5 stages.

A. Data Preparation

1) *Data Acquisition*: Spatial datasets were acquired to represent four dimensions of vertipoint suitability: (i) transportation accessibility (road network, railway infrastructure, and public transport stations), (ii) activity intensity (points of interest that represent destinations for which accessibility is evaluated.), (iii) land-use compatibility (commercial, industrial, and open land types), and (iv) separation from

environmentally or socially sensitive areas (e.g., residential zones, protected areas, schools, and healthcare facilities).

All datasets were obtained from Open Street Map (OSM), as summarized in Table I. Vector datasets were processed in Shapefile (SHP) format for compatibility with raster-based spatial analysis and subsequent distance accumulation modeling. A 50 m resolution digital elevation model, which provides globally consistent radar-derived topographic data originally collected by NASA’s The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM), was incorporated as a surface raster to enable terrain-adjusted distance accumulation.

TABLE I. Summary of Input Layers for Suitability Modeling

Dataset	Source	Feature Type
Road network	OpenStreetMap	Line
Public transport stations	OpenStreetMap	Point
Railway infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	Line
Land use features	OpenStreetMap	Polygon
Points of interest	OpenStreetMap	Point
Digital terrain model	SRTM (OpenDEM)	Raster

Features were selected based on established IAM vertipoint siting criteria reported in prior studies [4], [12], [26] to capture multimodal integration potential, demand proximity, land-use suitability, and separation from incompatible uses.

2) *Projection & Harmonization*: All datasets were re-projected from World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84) (EPSG:4326) to the projected metric coordinate reference system of the study region to enable planar distance computations and minimize spatial distortion at the regional scale.

A uniform spatial resolution of 50 m was selected to match the native resolution of the SRTM, balancing detail and computational cost. The SRTM raster served as the reference grid to ensure cell alignment across all rasterized layers.

B. Proximity-Based Criteria Structuring

OSM datasets contain attributes describing functional characteristics (e.g., road class, land-use category, facility type). Vertipoint suitability depends on functional attributes, not only geometry. Based on IAM siting principles [26], attribute values were classified into two proximity classes: Near and Far. Near-class features increase suitability with proximity; Far-class features increase suitability with distance. Table II documents the complete rule-based mapping between input datasets, attribute values, and assigned proximity preferences.

C. Terrain-Aware Distance Modeling

1) *Distance Accumulation Analysis*: After proximity-based classification, spatial relationships were converted to continuous distance surfaces using ArcGIS distance accumulation [27]. This raster-based method computes, for each grid cell, the accumulated distance to source features while incorporating terrain constraints from the 50 m SRTM digital elevation model provided as the input surface raster. Cell to cell transitions were adjusted according to local elevation differences, ensuring that accumulated distances reflect 3D terrain-adjusted path lengths rather than planar distances [28].

TABLE II. Attribute-based classification of spatial features into proximity suitability criteria

No	Input Data	Proximity Suitability	Attribute Values
1	Road network	Near	Motorway, primary, secondary, trunk, pedestrian
2	Road network	Far	Residential roads
3	Railway infrastructure	Near	Rail, light rail, tram, funicular, narrow gauge
4	Public transport stations	Near	Airport, bus station/stop, ferry terminal, railway station, tram stop, helipad
5	Points of interest	Near	Activity centers, demand hubs
6	Points of interest	Far	Noise-sensitive or low-activity areas
7	Land use features	Near	Commercial, industrial, retail, meadow, grass, scrub
8	Land use features	Far	Residential, forest, park, cemetery, military, nature reserve

Importantly, elevation influences the calculation only through the geometric properties of the terrain surface, without introducing slope-dependent impedance or additional cost assumptions. Consequently, in areas of substantial relief the accumulated surface distance is strictly greater than the planar distance and better reflects the true ground travel path length. Compared with conventional Euclidean distance, which measures straight-line proximity in two-dimensional space, this approach yields slightly larger distance values in sloped areas due to longer paths across the terrain surface (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Conceptual representation of terrain-aware Distance Accumulation modeling

Distance accumulation was computed independently for each categorized layer using the parameters summarized in Table III.

The resulting eight terrain-aware rasters (Table IV) serve as inputs for normalization and spatial dimensionality reduction.

2) *Normalization to Common Suitability Scale:* Distance accumulation rasters exhibit different value ranges based on spatial distribution. To prevent scale-dependent bias in multivariate analysis, all rasters were normalized to a 0-1 scale using min-max transformation (Table V).

TABLE III. Distance Accumulation Analysis Parameters

Component	Setting	Purpose
Input layers	Categorized feature/raster classes	Independent Distance Accumulation modeling
Surface model	Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	Surface-based distance computation
Distance method	Planar	Linear metric distance calculation
Cell size	50 m	Spatial resolution consistency
Snap raster	Reference grid	Cell alignment
Mask	Analysis boundary	Spatial constraint
Resampling	Nearest neighbor	Preserve categorical integrity

TABLE IV. Transformation of input layers into terrain-aware distance accumulation rasters

No	Input Layer	Distance Accumulation Analysis Output
1	Road Network (Near)	Road Network (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster
2	Road Network (Far)	Road Network (Far) Distance Accumulation Raster
3	Railway Infrastructure (Near)	Railway Infrastructure (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster
4	Public Transport Stations (Near)	Public Transport Stations (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster
5	Points of Interest (Near)	Points of Interest (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster
6	Points of Interest (Far)	Points of Interest (Far) Distance Accumulation Raster
7	Land Use Features (Near)	Land Use Features (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster
8	Land Use Features (Far)	Land Use Features (Far) Distance Accumulation Raster

For Far-type criteria (suitability increases with distance), normalization follows Equation 1.

$$S_{\text{far}} = \frac{d - d_{\text{min}}}{d_{\text{max}} - d_{\text{min}}} \quad (1)$$

For Near-type criteria (suitability decreases with distance), the inverse transformation (Equation 2) is applied so that higher values represent higher suitability across all criteria.

$$S_{\text{near}} = 1 - \frac{d - d_{\text{min}}}{d_{\text{max}} - d_{\text{min}}} \quad (2)$$

After transformation, higher values consistently represent higher suitability across all criteria, enabling their joint integration within the sPCA.

TABLE V. Normalization of Distance Accumulation Rasters

Input	Method	Output
8 Distance rasters (Near/Far criteria)	Min-max normalization (Eq. 1-2)	8 Suitability rasters (0-1 scale)

This linear rescaling provides a transparent, parameter-free mapping that preserves rank order within each criterion and enables joint analysis in sPCA. However, distance–suitability relationships may be non-linear; alternative formulations (e.g., piecewise-linear or sigmoidal functions with threshold effects) could be explored in future work.

D. Spatial Dimensionality Reduction

The eight normalized suitability rasters from Table IV form a multivariate spatial dataset requiring dimensionality reduction for computational efficiency. This section describes spatial aggregation, weight matrix construction, and sPCA used to extract composite suitability indices.

1) *Spatial Aggregation*: To reduce computational complexity while preserving regional patterns, the normalized 50 m rasters were aggregated to a 500 m grid using mean aggregation. This reduced the number of spatial units and enabled construction of the spatial weight matrix for sPCA.

2) *Spatial Weight Matrix Construction*: A K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) approach defined fixed-degree connectivity across the 500 m grid, ensuring uniform neighborhood size regardless of edge effects or boundary irregularities.

KNN produces an asymmetric neighborhood structure where cell i may neighbor j without reciprocity. To satisfy the undirected graph requirement of sPCA, the structure was symmetrized, converting unidirectional connections ($i \rightarrow j$) to bidirectional relationships ($i \leftrightarrow j$).

The number of neighbors (k) was determined through sensitivity analysis of $k = 6$ (hexagonal), $k = 8$ (queen-type), and $k = 10$ (extended neighborhood). For each configuration, sPCA was performed and component structures were assessed using Moran’s I statistics and loading stability.

The $k = 8$ configuration was selected, corresponding to queen-type adjacency encompassing all orthogonal and diagonal neighbors (Figure 3). This balances spatial detail and computational efficiency.

Figure 3. Queen-type neighborhood structure ($k = 8$) showing orthogonal and diagonal adjacencies in a regular grid.

The symmetrized structure was converted into a spatial weight matrix $W = [w_{ij}]$, where w_{ij} represents the connection between cells i and j . Row-standardization was applied ($\sum_j w_{ij} = 1$), ensuring weights sum to unity and allowing spatial lags to represent local neighborhood averages.

3) *Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA)*: sPCA was applied to reduce the dimensionality of the eight normalized suitability rasters. In spatial datasets, multiple criteria often exhibit correlation and spatial dependence, which may lead to redundancy when aggregated directly. Unlike conventional PCA, sPCA incorporates spatial autocorrelation

through the spatial weight matrix W , extracting components that maximize both statistical variance and spatial structure [29]. This procedure reduces multicollinearity among criteria while retaining spatially structured variability relevant for regional suitability assessment. The analysis was implemented in R using the `spca()` function from the `ade4` package.

a) *Scaling*:: The aggregated 500 m rasters were z-score standardized (mean = 0, standard deviation = 1) prior to PCA. Standardization ensures equal variance contributions across criteria, preventing variables with larger dispersion from dominating component extraction.

b) *sPCA Computation*:: sPCA was applied to the scaled data matrix using the spatial weight matrix W . The resulting components are associated with eigenvalues that reflect the joint maximization of variance and spatial autocorrelation:

$$\lambda = \text{var}(Xv) \cdot I(Xv) \quad (3)$$

where X is the scaled data matrix, v is the eigenvector, and $I(Xv)$ is Moran’s I statistic. Positive eigenvalues indicate global structures (positive autocorrelation); negative eigenvalues indicate local structures (negative autocorrelation). Only components with positive eigenvalues were retained, as global patterns are relevant for regional siting.

c) *Component Retention*: Component retention was based on cumulative explained variance. Components were retained until the cumulative sum of positive eigenvalues exceeded 70% of total variance, a standard threshold in spatial analysis [30]. This criterion was evaluated across all three KNN configurations ($k = 6, 8, 10$) to assess stability.

d) *Score Extraction*: For each retained component, two score types were obtained: noitemsep

- **Raw scores (l_r)**: Direct projection of cell values onto component axes, representing local statistical contributions.
- **Lagged scores (l_s)**: Spatially weighted averages computed as $l_s = Wl_r$, where W denotes the row-standardized spatial weight matrix. These scores incorporate neighborhood effects and exhibit enhanced spatial smoothness.

Both score types were extracted as raster layers. Raw scores preserve local variation and were used for site identification; lagged scores provide spatially coherent patterns for regional interpretation.

e) *Component Selection for Site Extraction*: Although multiple components were retained to summarize spatially structured variance, only the first axis (Axis 1) was used for candidate site delineation. Axis 1 represents the dominant suitability gradient and captures the primary spatial structure relevant for regional infrastructure planning. Higher-order components describe secondary spatial patterns and were therefore not considered for the extraction of candidate sites, in order to preserve interpretability and focus on the principal geographic suitability structure.

4) *Candidate Site Extraction*:

a) *Spatial Autocorrelation*: Prior to candidate delineation, the spatial structure of Axis 1 scores was assessed using Global Moran's I . The statistic evaluates whether high or low suitability values are spatially clustered beyond random expectation by incorporating the predefined spatial weight matrix. A statistically significant positive Moran's I indicates the presence of spatially coherent suitability clusters, supporting the extraction of geographically contiguous candidate zones. The methodological rationale for applying Moran's I in vertiport-related spatial analysis is discussed in our previous work [31].

b) *Percentile-Based Thresholding*: Candidate sites were identified by percentile-based thresholding of Component 1 raw scores (I_i). Cells exceeding specified percentiles were classified as high-suitability areas. Three thresholds (top 1%, 5%, and 10%) were evaluated to assess sensitivity to selectivity parameters.

The 1% threshold was selected based on: (1) compact spatial extent, (2) manageable polygon count (< 300 polygons), and (3) preservation of high-confidence suitability peaks (scores > 2.3 standard deviations above the mean).

c) *Polygon Generation*: Selected high-suitability cells were aggregated into contiguous patches using queen-type (8-neighbor) adjacency, merging adjacent cells into unified polygons representing spatial suitability zones. No minimum patch size constraint was imposed, allowing all spatially contiguous suitability clusters to be retained.

d) *Centroid Extraction*: For each suitability polygon, a geometric centroid was computed to represent the candidate vertiport location.

e) *Output Format*: The candidate set was exported as SHP containing both polygon geometries (suitability zones) and point geometries (centroids).

IV. RESULTS

A. Study Area

The proposed framework was applied to the federal state of Saxony in eastern Germany. The region covers approximately 18,450 km² and has a population of about 4.1 million [32]. The spatial structure of the State of Saxony is based on an administrative division consisting of 10 districts (Landkreis) and 3 independent cities (Chemnitz, Dresden, Leipzig) [33]. Saxony features a dense multimodal transportation network, including extensive road and railway infrastructure, providing a suitable spatial context for regional vertiport network analysis.

The availability of consistent geospatial datasets from OSM and high-resolution terrain models enables a fully reproducible implementation of the proposed terrain-aware suitability framework. Consequently, Saxony represents a realistic and data-consistent test environment for evaluating large-scale vertiport site selection and pre-optimization spatial filtering.

B. Data Preparation

OSM-derived datasets (roads, railways, stations, land use, POIs) and 50 m SRTM terrain data were compiled and projected to European Terrestrial Reference System 1989

Figure 4. Normalized terrain-aware distance accumulation surfaces for the spatial criteria. All rasters were scaled to the 0-1 range, where higher values (green) indicate greater suitability.

(ETRS89) / The Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) Zone 33N for metric consistency.

C. Proximity-Based Criteria Structuring

Each feature attribute in the dataset was classified based on proximity criteria as "Near" (favorable proximity) or "Far" (unfavorable proximity) for vertiport placement.

D. Terrain-Aware Distance Modeling

Distance accumulation was performed using the 50 m SRTM surface within the Saxony boundary, producing eight terrain-aware distance surfaces corresponding to Near/Far suitability classes. After min-max normalization to a 0-1 scale (higher values indicate higher suitability), these layers formed the standardized input for sPCA. Normalized surfaces are shown in Figure 4.

E. Spatial Dimensionality Reduction

1) *Spatial Aggregation*: The normalized 50 m rasters were aggregated to a 500 m grid using a 10×10 mean resampling window. This reduced the number of spatial units from approximately 7,494,400 to 74,944 cells (–99%), improving computational efficiency while preserving regional suitability gradients.

2) *Spatial Weight Matrix Construction*: Table VI shows strong robustness across neighborhood specifications. Cumulative explained variance, Moran’s I , and the number and extent of selected candidate patches vary only marginally among $k = 6, 8, \text{ and } 10$. This indicates that the suitability are insensitive to neighborhood parameterization. The $k = 8$ configuration was retained for subsequent analyses.

TABLE VI. KNN Sensitivity Analysis Results

k	Cumulative Variance (%)	Moran’s I (Axis 1)	Candidate Patches	Total Area (km ²)
6	77.63	0.796	236	187.4
8	77.67	0.793	236	187.4
10	78.18	0.760	235	187.4

3) Spatial Principal Component Analysis (sPCA):

a) *Scaling*: Z-score standardization was applied to the eight aggregated criteria. Post-scaling validation confirmed that all criteria exhibited means within machine precision of zero ($|\text{mean}| < 10^{-15}$) and standard deviations of exactly 1.00 (Table VII), satisfying the centering requirements for covariance-based PCA.

TABLE VII. Descriptive Statistics of All Input Criteria

Criteria	Mean (scaled)	SD (scaled)
Land Use (Far)	8.40×10^{-18}	1.00
Land Use (Near)	-4.32×10^{-16}	1.00
POI (Far)	1.01×10^{-16}	1.00
POI (Near)	-2.02×10^{-16}	1.00
Railway Infrastructure (Near)	-2.14×10^{-16}	1.00
Road Network (Far)	4.39×10^{-18}	1.00
Road Network (Near)	-4.99×10^{-17}	1.00
Transit Station (Near)	-5.00×10^{-16}	1.00

b) *sPCA Computation*: The sPCA decomposition yielded four positive eigenvalues corresponding to global spatial structures. Negative eigenvalues (local patterns) were excluded due to the regional planning focus. Table VIII presents the eigenvalue decomposition for the baseline configuration ($k = 8$).

TABLE VIII. sPCA Eigenvalue Decomposition ($k = 8$)

Axis	Eigenvalue	Variance (%)	Cumulative (%)	Moran’s I (li)
1	2.493	40.40	40.40	0.793
2	0.891	14.44	54.84	0.851
3	0.770	12.48	67.32	–
4	0.639	10.35	77.67	–

Axis 1 dominates the decomposition, accounting for 40.4% of variance with strong positive spatial autocorrelation (Moran’s $I = 0.793$). This indicates a statistically and spatially coherent suitability gradient. Axis 2 exhibits stronger

spatial autocorrelation (Moran’s $I = 0.851$) but contributes substantially less variance (14.4%). Components 3–4 explain progressively smaller variance and were not prioritized.

c) *Component Retention*: Four components were retained, cumulatively explaining 77.67% of total variance for the baseline configuration ($k = 8$). This remained stable across neighborhood definitions, with cumulative variance ranging between 77.6% and 78.2% across alternative k values (Table VI).

d) *Score Extraction*: For each axis, two score types were extracted: raw scores (li) representing direct projections, and lagged scores (ls) incorporating neighborhood averaging. Table IX presents descriptive statistics for Axis 1.

TABLE IX. Axis 1 Score Statistics ($k = 8$)

Score Type	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Moran’s I
Raw (li)	0.00	1.00	–2.43	6.76	0.793
Lagged (ls)	0.00	0.93	–2.27	5.70	0.943

Lagged scores exhibit higher spatial autocorrelation than raw scores, reflecting neighborhood smoothing. Raw scores were used for candidate identification to preserve local variation, while lagged scores were retained for visualization.

e) *Axis Selection*: Axis 1 was selected for candidate extraction based on its dominant contribution to variance (40.40%) and strong positive spatial autocorrelation (Moran’s $I = 0.793$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). While Axis 2 exhibited higher spatial structure ($I = 0.851$), it explained substantially less variance (14.44%) and was therefore not prioritized.

f) *Axis Interpretation*: As shown in Table X, Axis 1 represents the primary accessibility–suitability gradient, contrasting spatial units characterized by high multimodal connectivity with comparatively isolated areas. The selection of candidate sites is directly influenced by the variable loadings: proximity-based variables (e.g., Public Transport Stations (Near), Road Network (Near), and Points of Interest (Near) exhibit strong negative loadings, indicating that shorter distances to transport infrastructure and activity centers correspond to lower Axis scores. Because the suitability procedure prioritizes lower Axis 1 values, these negative loadings increase the likelihood that well-connected locations are retained within the candidate set.

Conversely, the positive loading on Road Network (Far) indicates that increasing distance from major road infrastructure raises the Axis score. Under the adopted thresholding rule, spatial units exhibiting greater infrastructural isolation are therefore less likely to satisfy the high-suitability criterion. In this sense, Axis 1 functions as an accessibility–isolation gradient governing spatial filtering in vertiport siting.

Axis 2 captures a secondary spatial structure primarily associated with Railway Infrastructure (Near) and Points of Interest (Far). This Axis identifies rail-accessible areas located at greater distance from dense urban activity centers. However, since candidate extraction was based exclusively on Axis 1 scores, Axis 2 does not directly determine the final candidate set and instead reflects complementary spatial variation within the study area.

4) Candidate Site Extraction:

TABLE X. Principal Axis Loadings of Vertiport Suitability Variables

Variable	Axis 1	Axis 2
Public Transport Stations (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-0.481	-
Points of Interest (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-0.394	-
Road Network (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-0.383	-
Road Network (Far) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	0.481	-
Land Use (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-0.301	-
Railway Infrastructure (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-0.284	-
Points of Interest (Far) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-	0.710
Railway Infrastructure (Near) Distance Accumulation Raster Data	-	0.553

a) *Spatial Autocorrelation Validation:* Moran’s I statistic confirmed significant positive spatial autocorrelation in Axis 1 scores (Moran’s $I = 0.793$, $p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$), indicating non-random geographic clustering of high-suitability areas.

b) *Percentile Threshold Selection:* Three percentile thresholds (1%, 5%, and 10%) were evaluated based on Axis 1 score distributions (Table XI). The 1% threshold, corresponding to Axis 1 scores ≤ -2.373 , was selected for final analysis. This threshold isolated approximately 750 cells (1% of 74,944 non-NA cells), representing the most statistically extreme suitability clusters.

TABLE XI. Percentile Threshold Score Cutoffs (Axis 1, $k = 8$)

Threshold	Score Cutoff	Cells Selected
1%	≤ -2.373	750
5%	≤ -2.068	3,750
10%	≤ -1.771	7,500

Polygon generation and spatial analysis were performed exclusively for the 1% threshold. Higher thresholds (5%, 10%) were not polygonized, as the study prioritizes high-selectivity candidate sets to minimize computational burden in subsequent optimization stages.

c) *Polygon Generation:* High-suitability cells identified by the 1% threshold were spatially aggregated into contiguous patches using queen-type (8-neighbor) adjacency. This operation merged approximately 750 individual cells into 236 unified polygons, covering a total area of 187.4 km².

Figure 5 illustrates the spatial distribution of Axis 1 suitability scores. Green areas represent higher vertiport suitability. These patterns reflect the accessibility-driven gradient captured by Axis 1, with high-suitability zones systematically co-located with transportation infrastructure and activity centers.

d) *Candidate Site Summary Statistics:* The 236 candidate polygons exhibit a mean area of 0.79 km² (Table XII). All polygons satisfy the score threshold criterion (Axis 1 ≤ -2.373), ensuring uniform suitability qualification across the candidate set.

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of Axis 1 suitability scores derived from sPCA. Green areas indicate lower scores and therefore higher vertiport suitability.

TABLE XII. Candidate Site Summary Statistics (1% Threshold, $k = 8$)

Metric	Value
Number of polygons	236
Number of centroids	236
Total area (km ²)	187.4
Mean polygon area (km ²)	0.79
Median polygon area (km ²)	0.11
Min polygon area (km ²)	0.0025
Max polygon area (km ²)	42.17
Score threshold (Axis 1)	≤ -2.373

e) *Centroid Extraction:* For each polygon, a geometric centroid was computed to represent the candidate vertiport location.

The final candidate set, comprising 236 centroid points, represents a 99.7% reduction from the original 74,944-cell decision space (750 cells selected, aggregated into 236 polygons). This compression substantially reduces the combinatorial complexity of subsequent facility location models while preserving geographically realistic and statistically validated high-suitability zones.

Figure 6 shows the spatial distribution of the 236 candidate vertiport centroids. The candidates exhibit clustered patterns consistent with the underlying Axis 1 scores. This distribution reflects the combined effects of accessibility advantages and constraint avoidance, producing a geographically realistic candidate set for network optimization.

F. Computational Impact of Candidate Reduction

To quantify the computational benefit of suitability-driven filtering, the same MILP formulation was solved using both the full grid and the filtered candidate set under identical solver configurations (IBM ILOG CPLEX, AMD EPYC 7513, 128 GB RAM). Results demonstrate that the two-order-of-magnitude reduction in binary variables transforms a computationally intractable problem into one solvable within minutes (Table XIII).

The filtering stage restricts the feasible region and does not guarantee preservation of the global optimum, and a direct optimality comparison is not feasible because the full-grid

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of 236 candidate vertiport centroids extracted from high-suitability zones (Axis 1 scores ≤ -2.373 , corresponding to the lowest 1% of the score distribution).

TABLE XIII. Effect of Candidate Filtering on MILP Tractability

Stage	Candidates	Binary Vars	Status	Runtime
Raw grid	74,944	1,572,203	Time limit	>96 h
Filtered	236	~5,000	Optimal	18 min

formulation does not converge. Nevertheless, the decisive factor behind the observed computational speed-up is the drastic reduction in the number of candidate locations entering the MILP: although the full grid contains 74,944 cells, the proposed filtering reduces this to 236 candidates ($\approx 99.7\%$), thereby directly decreasing the number of binary variables and, consequently, the computational effort.

V. DISCUSSION

The proposed methodology demonstrates how terrain-aware distance accumulation and sPCA can systematically reduce the combinatorial complexity of vertiport network optimization. By integrating terrain-constrained distance metrics with eigenvalue decomposition, eight correlated suitability criteria were synthesized into statistically independent components while preserving spatial autocorrelation structure. This data-driven aggregation reduces subjectivity relative to expert-weighted multi-criteria approaches and provides a reproducible spatial pre-screening methodology.

As demonstrated in the Results section, spatial filtering substantially improves computational tractability of the MILP formulation. While exact branch-and-bound solvers suffer from combinatorial growth in NP-hard facility location problems, heuristic or metaheuristic approaches could alternatively be employed on the full grid. However, such approaches sacrifice optimality guarantees. The present filtering strategy instead reduces the decision space prior to optimization while preserving an exact solution within the restricted candidate set.

Nevertheless, this spatial reduction introduces an inherent trade-off between computational tractability and global optimality. By constraining the MILP to the top 1% of suitability peaks, the feasible region is restricted. Consequently, the approach does not formally guarantee preservation of the

global optimum from the unrestricted candidate set. It remains theoretically possible that configurations composed of individually lower-ranked locations could collectively yield superior network solutions. Given that the unrestricted model did not converge within the imposed time limit, such comparisons are computationally infeasible at regional scale. The filtering procedure should therefore be interpreted as a heuristic pre-optimization reduction strategy that prioritizes computational tractability over exhaustive global search.

Compared with heuristic clustering or proximity-based screening, sPCA provides a statistically grounded synthesis that explicitly accounts for multicollinearity and spatial dependence. The resulting candidate set exhibits geographically coherent structures validated by Moran's I statistics, reducing the likelihood of fragmented or spatially inconsistent site configurations.

The methodology enables systematic integration of heterogeneous spatial datasets through reproducible computational pipelines (R, ArcGIS). By restricting optimization inputs to locations satisfying predefined spatial suitability criteria, the approach reduces computational burden while preserving spatial autocorrelation structure. The methodology is transferable to other metropolitan regions facing infrastructure siting problems under multiple correlated spatial constraints.

Several limitations warrant consideration. The analysis relies on open-source spatial datasets, which may introduce positional inaccuracies or incomplete coverage in certain areas. The suitability model prioritizes static proximity and land-use criteria but does not incorporate dynamic demand patterns, noise propagation, or regulatory airspace constraints. Spatial resolution (500 m aggregation) balances computational efficiency with geographic detail but may obscure fine-scale variations relevant to site-specific implementation.

Future research should extend the methodology to incorporate environmental impact assessments (e.g., noise exposure and visual intrusion), meteorological constraints (wind exposure, visibility, adverse weather), and broader airspace structure considerations such as obstacle clearance and controlled airspace boundaries. Integrating dynamic demand forecasting and multi-objective optimization frameworks (e.g., equity, resilience, robustness) would further enhance operational realism and policy relevance. Coupling the spatial filtering stage with agent-based simulation or traffic flow models could enable evaluation of network performance under realistic operational conditions, thereby bridging the gap between static site selection and dynamic system behavior.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presented a terrain-aware and data-driven spatial framework for vertiport site selection within Innovative Air Mobility systems. By integrating terrain-based distance accumulation with Spatial Principal Component Analysis, heterogeneous and correlated suitability criteria were systematically synthesized into geographically coherent suitability patterns.

The proposed filtering strategy reduced the initial feasible grid to a compact set of optimization-ready candidate locations, substantially shrinking the spatial decision space. This

reduction markedly improves computational tractability while preserving operational feasibility and geographic realism.

Beyond enhancing spatial realism, the framework significantly improves computational performance, transforming an otherwise computationally prohibitive MILP formulation into a tractable optimization problem. This enables large-scale IAM network design that would be impractical under direct full-grid optimization.

Overall, the framework establishes a reproducible bridge between GIS-based spatial analytics and optimization-driven network design, providing a scalable and transferable methodology for data-driven infrastructure planning in emerging regional air mobility systems.

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